

Well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim: A study in post COVID-19 pandemic period

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Abstract

This study examines the level of well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim, using a sample of 378 students from 54 schools. The well-being index (Wbi-cs) by Chouhan and Sharma (2016). was used for data collection. The results demonstrate that the majority of Sikkim's secondary school students obtain an above average level well-being. Furthermore, the study finds no significant impact of gender and locale on their well-being level. This research represents the importance of students' well-being in education.

Keywords: Well-being, secondary school students of Sikkim, COVID-19 and pandemic

Introduction

In December 2019, a novel coronavirus disease was first reported in Wuhan, China (Zhou *et al.*, 2020) ^[1]. This isolated virus was initially identified as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARSCoV-2), and it was officially named corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) by World Health Organisation in 2020. COVID-19 had a broad and long impact on people, with over 76 million people across 222 countries having been infected as of December 2020 (WHO, 2020) ^[10]. The year 2020 will be remembered as the year of the pandemic and will go down in history because more than 1.5 billion people around the planet were confined to stop the spread of SARS-CoV2, the causal agent of COVID-19 (Huh, 2020) ^[3].

The students of today are the citizens of tomorrow (Koyyani, 2020) ^[4]. The future citizens deserve a healthy, joyful and well-balanced life. Myers and Diener (1995) ^[6] states that positive state of well-being works as a fuel for leading a peaceful life. Thus, it is mainly described as a positive state of human being. The Programme for International Student Assessment (2008) framework on well-being measured well-being on three dimensions: a) self: how fit and healthy students perceive about themselves and their lives, b) School environment: an environmental

condition that is exposed to students at school and c) out-of-school environment: students living environment outside of school (OECD, 2017) ^[17]. Well-being in school can be perceived as dynamic and contextual state of mind which is manifested in students' self-efficacy to fulfil students' needs, sustain and succeed to the demands of the school (Pietarinen 2014) ^[8]. A safe learning environment with necessary school infrastructure, resources for learning and programmes help enhance students' physical, cognitive and well-being (Awartani, 2008) ^[1]. Hence, students are to be encouraged to participate in physical activities and bring awareness to healthy eating behaviours and balanced diet. Thus, well-being is multidimensional construct that facilitates to produce better learning outcomes in the young learning population across the young learning organisations. The term well-being is mostly used for specific variety of goodness such as living in a good environment being of worth for the world, being able to cope with life, enjoying life. The concept of well-being refers to optimum psychological functioning and experiences (Ryan & Deci, 2001) ^[9]. Keyes and Waterman (2003) ^[5] states that well-being encompasses social, emotional, psychological and physical aspects that help shape overall positive life functioning.

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the level of well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim in post COVID-19 pandemic period.
2. To study the difference in well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim in post COVID19 pandemic period in relation to gender.
3. To study the difference in well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim in post COVID19 pandemic period in relation to locale.

Hypotheses

H0₁: There is no significant difference in well-being between male and female secondary school students in post COVID-19 pandemic period.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in well-being between rural and urban secondary school Students in post COVID-19 pandemic period.

Materials and Methods

To study the well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim in post COVID pandemic period in relation to gender and locale. The investigator adopted descriptive survey method. Descriptive designs are set out to establish associations between variables and describe and interpret what is in a specific situation (Cohen, 2010) [2]. They are often used to identify problems for further and more sophisticated research. A sample of 378 secondary school students studying in 54 schools of Sikkim was selected using multistage random sampling technique. Well-being index (Wbi-cs) by Chouhan and Sharma (2016) [12] was used to measure the level of well-being of secondary school students. This is a fivepoint Scale. These options are-always, often, sometimes, rarely and never. Test-retest reliability of the scale is 0.71 and the validity of the scale is 0.85. For statistical analysis, the researcher calculated the mean, median and standard deviation. The mean and variance were then analysed based on gender and locale. 'T' test was performed, and conclusions were drawn by referring to tabulated values to determine significant differences among the subgroups. The interpretations of the findings, based on the statistical analysis are presented below:

Table 1: Details of the Sample

Sl. No.	Variables	Groups	No. of samples
1	Gender	Male	167
		Female	211
2	Locale	Urban	122
		Rural	256
Total sample			378

Findings of the Study

Objective 1: To find out the level of well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim in post COVID-19 pandemic period.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage on level of well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim.

Sr. No.	Range of Z-Scores	Grade	Level of Well Being	f	%
1.	+2.01 and above	A	Extremely High	13	3.43
2.	+1.26 to +2.00	B	High	119	31.48
3.	+0.51 to +1.25	C	Above Average	220	58.20
4.	-0.50 to +0.50	D	Average	26	6.87
5.	-1.25 to -0.51	E	Below Average	0	0
6.	-2.00 to -1.26	F	Low	0	0
7.+	-2.01 and below	G	Extremely Low	0	0

Students' level of well-being is divided into seven levels in the table above. It was found that majority of secondary school students of Sikkim have an above average level of well-being. 58% had an above average level of well-being, 31% had high level of well-being and 3% had an extremely high level of well-being.

Objective 2: To study the difference in well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim in post COVID-19 pandemic period in relation to gender.

Table 3: Summary of test of significance of difference between mean scores of the total sample due to gender variations on well-being

Categories	n	Mean	SD	't'	Remarks
Male	167	161.63	11.14	0.583	Not Significant at 0.05 level
Female	211	162.31	11.32		

From the above table, it was revealed that the value of 't' is 0.583 and is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states, "There is no significant difference in well-being between male and female secondary school students" failed to be rejected.

Objective 3: To study the difference in well-being among secondary school students of Sikkim in post COVID-19 pandemic period in relation to locale.

Table 4: Summary of test of significance of difference between mean scores of the total sample due to locale variations on well-being

Categories	n	Mean	SD	't'	Remarks
rural	122	161.90	10.15	0.248	Not Significant at 0.05 level
urban	256	162.31	12.66		

From the above table, it was revealed that the value of 't' is 0.248 and is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states, "There is no significant difference in well-being between rural and urban secondary school students" failed to be rejected.

Discussion

- Secondary school students of Sikkim were found to have an above average level of well-being. This may be because they have been exposed to educational initiatives,

discussions that have helped raise their awareness on the importance and need to have a good physical, mental, emotional, social and self-awareness to have a healthy and balanced day to day life and also, to excel in academic field. Additionally, Sikkim's various initiatives like yoga lesson and sports period might play a role in protecting a sense of good health and teamwork with leads to wellbeing among the students.

- No significant difference was found in well-being between male and female secondary school students. Gender does not affect their well-being. This may be because the educational institutions in Sikkim provide anti-discrimination and gender equality, ensuring that both male and female students receive equal care and rights to understand and learn importance of wellbeing. Additionally, the curriculum and teaching methodologies may be designed to be impartial and sensitive to gender-related topics, promoting an environment where all students can equally participate and embrace learning various ways to keep oneself in good shape. Furthermore, the presence of diverse extracurricular activities offered in schools irrespective of gender, might have positively influenced the students' perception towards having a good health. As a result, both male and female secondary school students have indicated comparable levels of well-being.
- No significant difference was found in well-being between rural and urban secondary school students, suggesting that place of residence does not affect their level of well-being. This may be because educational institutions and health programs in Sikkim have been implemented uniformly across both rural and urban areas, ensuring equal access to information and resources related to well-being. Additionally, advancements in technology and communication have likely bridged the gap between rural and urban communities, enabling students from both backgrounds to access similar educational content and engage in discussions related to importance of well-being. Furthermore, the various activities and societal norms in Sikkim may emphasize the importance of well-being and equality, regardless of one's place of residence, thereby contributing to a relatively balanced awareness on well-being level among secondary school students across the region.

Recommendation

- While the current study shows promising results regarding human rights awareness, there is room for improvement. Educational institutions in Sikkim should continue to prioritize human rights education, incorporating it into various disciplines and offering specialized courses that delve deeper into human rights issues. This would further foster critical thinking and a comprehensive understanding of human rights principles and their application in real-life scenarios.
- The study highlights that there is no significant difference in human rights awareness between male and female postgraduate students. To sustain this equality, educational institutions should ensure that the curriculum remains gender-inclusive and sensitive to gender-related topics. Additionally, promoting and

celebrating diverse role models and advocates for human rights, regardless of gender, can have a positive influence on students' perceptions and encourage greater engagement in human rights discussions.

- While the study finds no significant difference in human rights awareness between rural and urban postgraduate students, it is crucial to continue focusing on outreach programs in rural areas. Ensuring equal access to information and resources related to human rights can further elevate awareness levels among students from rural backgrounds. Leveraging technology and media can be instrumental in bridging the gap and reaching out to students residing in remote areas.
- To enhance human rights awareness, educational institutions can collaborate with civil society organizations and human rights activists. Guest lectures, workshops, and interactive sessions led by experts in the field can provide students with real-world insights and practical examples, enriching their understanding of human rights issues.
- Academic institutions can foster a deeper exploration of human rights by encouraging postgraduate students to choose human rights-related topics for their dissertations and research projects. This will not only contribute to the body of knowledge in this area but also nurture a culture of research and critical thinking regarding human rights concerns.
- Engaging with local communities and incorporating their perspectives on human rights can offer valuable insights to postgraduate students. Field visits, community engagement programs and internships in organizations working on human rights issues can deepen students' understanding and empathy towards these concerns.

Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed the existent need for increased well-being as secondary school students of Sikkim are above average in understanding the importance of well-being. The well-being of students was not found to be affected by gender or residence. This study underscores the urgency of strengthening significance of well-being in education and awareness among secondary school students of Sikkim. By enhancing their understanding of various facets of well-being, students can play a pivotal role in fostering a healthy life and excel in academic performance. The integrating of well-being in education into the curriculum, along with innovative approaches and collaborative initiatives, holds the potential to create a generation of knowledgeable citizens who can impart their knowledge confidently to their communities.

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